

The Influence of Work Discipline, Leadership Style, and Procedural Justice on the Performance of Employees of the Regional Environmental Agency of Karanganyar Regional

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to examine the extent to which work discipline, leadership style, and procedural justice influence the performance of employees at the Environmental Agency of Karanganyar Regency. A quantitative approach with a survey method was employed, involving the entire population of 84 employees as the research sample. Primary data were gathered through questionnaires completed by all respondents, supported by field observations as part of the data collection techniques. The results reveal that each variable work discipline, leadership style, and procedural justice—has a positive and significant individual impact on employee performance. Collectively, these three variables also contribute significantly to performance improvement, accounting for 60.7% of the variation in employee performance. Further analysis indicates that work discipline has the most substantial influence. Therefore, it is recommended that the Environmental Agency of Karanganyar consistently enforce discipline policies and provide regular training to enhance employee performance.

KEYWORDS: Leadership, Procedural Justice, Performance, Work Discipline.

INTRODUCTION

The Environmental Agency of Karanganyar Regional improving public services quality, particularly environmental management such as pollution control, waste management, nature conservation, and the arrangement of green open spaces. Through responsive programs based on community needs, the Karanganyar Environmental Agency strives to create a clean, healthy, and sustainable environment. The good performance of this agency is reflected in fast and transparent services, as well as involving community participation in maintaining the environment. Thus, the active role of the Environmental Agency not only impacts the creation of a better environment but also enhances community satisfaction and trust in public services overall. Performance refers to the outcomes achieved by employees as a reflection of their involvement within an organization. It serves as a measure of how effectively an individual carries out their duties in line with assigned responsibilities (Afandi, 2021). Hasibuan (2019) ask performance individual's efforts in performing tasks, shaped by their competence, level of effort, and the opportunities available. Challenges in achieving optimal employee performance are often attributed to both internal and external factors, notably including work discipline, leadership style, and procedural fairness.

Agustini (2019) ask discipline refers to an attitude of compliance norms and company rules, aimed at strengthening employee resilience in achieving organizational objectives. As a key operational function of human resource management, work discipline is essential for achieving strong job performance. It significantly contributes to enhancing employee performance by fostering professional attitudes and behaviors in the workplace. Discipline reflects an employee's commitment to following organizational rules, procedures, and responsibilities. Highly disciplined employees tend to be punctual, meet task deadlines, uphold work ethics, and perform consistently and purposefully. This directly contributes to improved productivity, operational efficiency, and the overall quality of work. Research findings by Setiawan et al. (2024) and Aprianto et al. (2024) demonstrate similar outcomes, showing that performance has a influence of discipline. But studies by Uleng et.al. (2023) and Muna and Isnowati (2022) report differing results, indicating performance does not have a significant impact of that work discipline.

Hasibuan (2021) defines leadership style as the manner in which a leader influences subordinate behavior to collaborate and contribute effectively toward achieving organizational goals. This includes a variety of approaches, such as autocratic, participative, and transformational leadership. Rivai (2021) similarly describes leadership style as a collection of traits and behaviors employed by a leader to guide subordinates in reaching organizational objectives. These perspectives highlight that leadership style is not fixed but varies depending on the situation. Therefore, leadership style can be understood as the combination of a leader's methods and

characteristics used to direct and motivate their team. An appropriate leadership style can foster a positive work atmosphere, promote effective communication, and encourage employee participation in decision-making processes. This, in turn, enhances employees' sense of ownership, accountability, and commitment to their work. Leaders who are able to tailor their leadership approach to suit organizational needs and the characteristics of their team members tend to achieve better overall performance outcomes.

Research conducted by Madicha and Dewi (2024) as well as Suwanto et al. (2024) supports this, indicating that leadership style positively affects employee performance. However, differing results were found in studies by Aziz and Putra (2022) and Yanti et al. (2022) concluded that performance does not have a significant effect of leadership style. In addition to work discipline and leadership style, procedural justice is another key factor that influences employee performance. Rahmawati (2020) defines procedural justice as an evaluation of the fairness of regulatory implementation, including opportunities for voicing opinions, the oversight of decisions, consistency in rule application, and the absence of bias. Fauziah (2021) adds that procedural justice involves the fairness of processes used in decision-making, which helps ensure that all organizational members feel involved and treated equitably.

Procedural fairness is significant because it may create a workplace where workers feel safe, valued, and respected to their work and the targets of the company when policies are implemented consistently, openly, and without bias. Therefore, well applied procedural fairness enhances performance by fostering a good and productive workplace culture. Empirical findings by Supriyadi et al. (2024) and Putra et al. (2023) affirm the positive impact employee performance of procedural justice. Conversely, Fauziah et al. (2023) and Khaliza et al. (2022) presents contrasting results, indicating no significant relationship.

Field observations at the Environmental Agency of Karanganyar Regency highlight several issues. These include employee tardiness, early departures, failure to record attendance, and inconsistent adherence to standard operating procedures. Some employees demonstrate low responsibility in meeting task deadlines. From a leadership perspective, poor communication between superiors and subordinates results in information gaps and coordination issues. There are also perceptions of unfair and non-transparent performance evaluations, with some employees feeling excluded from opportunities to express opinions or gain recognition.

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS

Employee Performance

Employee performance reflects the extent of the real contribution they make in the organizational wheel. According to Afandi (2021), performance shows how far a person is able to complete their tasks according to the responsibilities assigned. Meanwhile, Mangkunegara (2022) adds performance is not just the final result, but a reflection of dedication and responsibility in work.

Work Discipline

Work discipline is the main foundation for the creation of order and perseverance in an organization. Agustini (2019) views discipline as a manifestation of obedience to rules and norms in order to encourage the determination of employees. Meanwhile, Hasibuan (2017) emphasizes to adhere to organizational regulations and applicable social values. In short, discipline is not just about rules, but also a reflection of personal commitment to responsibility and workplace order.

Leadership Style

Leadership style reflects how a leader directs, influences, and inspires their team to achieve common goals. Edison (2016) views it as a pattern of actions and the approach of a leader in guiding organizational members. Meanwhile, Hasibuan (2016) emphasizes that leadership style is not just about providing direction, but also how a leader fosters morale, creates job satisfaction, and encourages high productivity for the overall success of the organization. In other words, leadership style is the art of leading with influence, not just commands.

Procedural Justice

Procedural justice is not just about rules, but about the sense of fairness in every decision-making process. Robbins and Judge (2018) explain that this fairness is reflected in the consistency of procedures, timeliness, neutrality, continuous improvement of rules, and ethics in its implementation. Meanwhile, Greenberg and Baron (2013) highlight that procedural justice arises from the perception that decisions are made fairly and without bias, so that both the organization and employees feel valued and benefited. In other words, procedural justice is the essence of ethical and transparent decision-making in the workplace.

FRAMEWORK OF RESEARCH AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Discipline is not just about being on time or obeying the rules it is a reflection of an employee's awareness and commitment to their responsibilities. According to Hasibuan (2020), discipline arises from the willingness to adhere to existing rules and social norms. Employees who exhibit strong discipline typically work in a more organized, efficient, and consistent manner when carrying out their responsibilities. It is therefore unsurprising that work discipline serves as a fundamental pillar in enhancing performance. According to research by Setiawan et.al.(2024) and Aprianto et.al.(2024), optimal performance when they are subjected to higher degrees of discipline.

Leadership style is the art of influence—how leaders act, provide direction, and inspire their teams. Edison (2016) states that effective leaders can create motivation and provide support, enabling employees to perform at their best. Good leadership also builds harmonious relationships, creates a healthy work environment, and encourages active involvement. This's consistent with a findings Madicha and Dewi (2024) as well as Suwanto et al. (2024), who come to the conclusion that leadership style impact to employee performance is significantly.

Procedural justice is not just about written rules, but also about how decision-making processes are carried out fairly, transparently, and with respect for all parties. According to Fauziyah (2021), when employees feel involved and treated fairly in the decision-making process, it will foster a sense of appreciation, trust, and equal treatment. This strengthens their loyalty, commitment, and work spirit. Fair procedures create a harmonious work environment, reduce the potential for conflict, and encourage employees to work more focused, responsibly, and productively. Supriyadi et al. (2024) and Putra et al. (2023) supports this demonstrating how performance is significantly impacted by procedural justice.

RESEARCH METHODS

Study's uses a survey method in a quantitative manner. The research sample consists of all 84 workers of the Environmental Agency of Karanganyar Regency. A questionnaire is used to gather primary data, and a Likert scale is used as the research tool and grading system. Validity and reliability are carried out to guarantee the quality of data. Furthermore, traditional assumption tests are conducted, such as testing for heteroscedasticity, multicollinearity, and normality. Linear regression and t-test for hypothesis testing, the simultan test for model testing, computation the coefficient of multiple determination are all part of data analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Validity Test Results

The results indicate that every statement item across all variables has a calculated r-value > 0.215. This permits the study to proceed to the following stage of testing by confirming that every item is deemed legitimate and suitable for usage.

Table 1. Validity Test Results

No	Variable	r calculate	r table
1	Work Discipline (X ₁)	0.838	0.215
		0.697	
		0.832	
		0.755	
		0.837	
2	Leadership Style (X ₂)	0.797	0.215
		0.859	
		0.873	
		0.850	
		0.872	
3	Procedural Justice (X ₃)	0.674	0.215
		0.695	
		0.685	
		0.708	
		0.676	
4	Performance Employee (Y)	0.693	0.215
		0.868	
		0.776	
		0.780	
		0.670	

Source: Primary data processing, Mei 2025

Reliability Test Results

According to the findings that the Cronbach's alpha (α) values for all variable up to 0.600. This suggests that the instrument items possess good internal consistency and are appropriate for use in the subsequent analysis stage.

Table 2. Reliability Test Results

No	Variable	Alpha
1	Work Discipline (X ₁)	0.851
2	Leadership Style (X ₂)	0.903
3	Procedural Justice (X ₃)	0.718
4	Employee Performance (Y)	0.817

Source: Primary data processing, Mei 2025

Normality Test Results

The result know all variabel have normally distributed, which show that the distribution of data points fits the pattern of a line diagonal. This is deemed suitable since assumption normalcy is satisfied, and the study can proceed to the following phase.

Figure 2. Normality Test Results

Results of Multicollinearity Test

The test findings show that variables procedural justice (X3), leadership style (X2), and work discipline (X1) all have VIF < 10 and tolerance > 0.01. This enables the study to proceed to the following step by Verifying that the variables do not exhibit multicollinearity

Table 3. Results of Multicollinearity Test

Variable / Item	Tolerance	VIF
Work Discipline (X ₁)	0.647	1.544
Leadership Style (X ₂)	0.619	1.616
Procedural Justice (X ₃)	0.781	1.280

Source: Primary data processing, Mei 2025

Results of the Heteroskedasticity Test

The data points seem to be randomly distributed around the zero value on the Y and don't establish any clear patterns., according heteroskedasticity test, which are displayed in the following figure. This implies that there are no heteroskedasticity problems with the data, therefore the analysis may proceed to the following step without encountering any problems.

Figure 3 Results of the Heteroskedasticity Test

Results of Model Test (F Test)

The significance value of 0.000 < 0.05, and the computed F value of 41.202 > 2.71, the model test results (F Test) suggests that work discipline (X1), leadership style (X2), and procedural justice (X3) is positively and significantly impacted on employee performance (Y). Consequently, it can be said that these three factors are essential to improving the work output of the Environmental Agency of Karanganyar Regency's staff.

Table 4. Results of Model Test (F Test)

	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	367.171	3	122.390	41.202	0.000
	Residual	237.638	80	2.970		
	Total	604.810	83			

Source: Primary data processing, Mei 2025

Results of the Coefficient of Determination (R²)

This's values shown in the table, is 0.607. This suggests that the three independent variables work discipline (X1), leadership style (X2), and procedural fairness (X3) can explain for around 60.7% of the variation in employee performance (Y). Other factors not included in this study, such as job satisfaction, stress, workload, employee competency, and other external variables, affect the remaining 39.3%.

Table 5. Results of the Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.779	0.607	0.592	1.72351

Source: Primary data processing, Mei 202

Results of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Results of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis:

Table 6. Results of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	
	B	Std. Error	Beta	
1	(Constant)	2.993	1.857	
	DK.X1	0.492	0.084	0.509
	GK.X2	0.189	0.071	0.236
	KPo.X3	0.205	0.084	0.193

Source: Primary data processing, Mei 2025

The results are known equality :

$$Y = 2.993 + 0.492X1 + 0.189X2 + 0.205X3 + e$$

The results are known :

1. The constant 2.993 even if the variables of work discipline (X1), leadership style (X2), and procedural fairness (X3) are all at zero.
2. The work discipline variable (X1) has a value (β) of 0.492. This indicates that employee performance to grow 0.492 for every unit increase in work discipline, while maintaining a steady leadership style and procedural justice.
3. A positive link is also shown by the leadership style variable's (X2) beta coefficient (β) of 0.189. Employee performance increases by 0.189 units for every unit rise in leadership style, when work discipline and procedural justice stay the same.
4. Additionally, the procedural justice variable (X3) shows a positive impact with a beta value (β) of 0.205. This suggests that increases procedural fairness result in a 0.205 increase on performance, with assuming work discipline and leadership style remain same.

Hypothesis Testing Results (T-Test)

Hypothesis Testing :

Table 7. Hypothesis Testing Results (T-Test)

Variabel	t _{hitung}	Sig.	t _{tabel}
Work Discipline (X ₁)	5.848	0.000	1.990
Leadership Style (X ₂)	2.654	0.010	1.990
Procedural Justice (X ₃)	2.438	0.017	1.990

Source: Primary data processing, Mei 2025

The above results can be explained:

1. The work discipline variable (X₁) has a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$, and a t-value of $5.848 > 1.990$. This suggests that X₁ significantly and favorably affects Y. This's approved, demonstrating work discipline at the Environmental Agency of Karanganyar Regency improves employee performance.
2. The leadership style variable (X₂) has a significant level of $0.010 < 0.05$, the leadership style variable (X₂) likewise displays $2.654 > 1.990$. This's employee performance (Y) is impacted positively and significantly of leadership style, at least in part. The Second Hypothesis (H₂), according to which employee performance is positively impacted by leadership style, is therefore validated.
3. The t-value of $2.438 > 1.990$ for the procedural justice variable (X₃). The sig. threshold is $0.017 < 0.05$ and then procedural fairness significantly and favorably affects employee performance (Y), at least in part. As a result, the Third Hypothesis (H₃) is approved, suggesting that procedural fairness enhances worker performance at the Karanganyar Regency Environmental Agency.

DISCUSSION

Work discipline shown by a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$, and a t-value $5.848 > 1.990$ t-table value. These imply that improved employee performance is a direct effect of increased job discipline, accountability for tasks, regulation compliance, and timeliness. Disciplined workers are more likely to be reliable, well-organized, and dedicated to their work, all of which improve performance as a whole. Although they are in contrast to studies by Uleng et al. (2023) and Muna & Isnowati (2022), which found no discernible impact of work discipline on performance. This result is consistent with those of Setiawan et al. (2024) and Aprianto et al. (2024). Leadership style (X₂) has a significant level of $0.010 < 0.05$ and t-value $2.654 > 1.990$ t-table value, the result give that good leadership enhances performance. A leader who inspires others, communicates clearly, and gives clear instructions creates a positive work atmosphere that raises output and quality of work. Studies by Madicha & Dewi (2024) and Suwanto et al. (2024) corroborate these findings. Finally, a significance level procedural justice has a sig. $0.017 < 0.05$ and a t-value of $2.438 > 1.990$ the t-table value, employee performance has a positive and substantial influence of procedural justice (X₃). According to this, workers who believe that organizational processes are fair—that is, when decisions are made in a clear, consistent, and unbiased manner are more likely to feel valued and inspired, which increases dedication and produces better job results. These findings are in line with those of Supriyadi et al. (2024) and Putra et al. (2023), who found evidence of a substantial correlation between employee performance and procedural justice.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion

Drawing from the analysis and discussion presented in the previous section, it can be concluded that all three independent variables have a favorable influence on employee performance at the Regional Environmental Agency of Karanganyar Regency. Firstly, work discipline has a significant and positive impact on how well employees perform. Secondly, leadership style also plays a crucial role, showing a meaningful and positive relationship with employee performance. Lastly, procedural justice contributes positively and significantly to enhancing the performance of the agency's personnel.

Suggestions

The Karanganyar Regional Environment Agency must improve the application of discipline through a reward-punishment system and frequent coaching to make personnel more responsible, on time, and compliant with rules. In order to produce motivating and flexible leaders, leaders are required to continuously honing their soft skills through training and to maintain a communicative and participatory leadership style. To keep employees feeling appreciated and inspired, procedural justice must be upheld by guaranteeing openness and impartiality in hiring, promotion, and performance reviews. It is suggested that future studies include other factors such corporate culture, work environment, and motivation.

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